

THE DESIGN PRINCIPLE AND WEAVING TECHNOLOGY OF THREAD-LINKED BOX-BEAM PREFORM

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SUMMARY: Thread-linked box-beam preform is a new structure textile. There are many threads between one pair opposite walls and these threads are woven together with the walls to form a three dimensional integrated structure. These threads not only link the two opposite walls but also keep them apart from a certain distance. The paper explores the principle of fabric forming and the weave structure developed by us, introduces the weaving process in detail and also discusses some problems which should be noticed in weaving with this new structure textile. It will certainly have a great value in developing and producing a new type of textile composites.

KEYWORDS: box-beam preform, thread-linked, design principle, weaving technique, woven, centre-weft-stitching, stitching place, fabric specifications

INTRODUCTION

Thread-linked box-beam preform is a new structure of textile preform. The traditional woven hollow fabric only has four connected walls which form a rectangle cross section. In this new structure, there are many threads between one pair opposite walls and these threads are woven together with the walls to form a three dimensional integrated structure. These threads not only link the two opposite walls but also keep them apart from a certain distance. The preform can be designed for specific applications such as a passage, a filter of gases or liquids, and a filling with sand, foam and so on, and its properties are varied by means of the material, fabric structure and thread arrangement. It can contain up to 160,000 thread stitching places per m^2 and can be produced with the spacing up to 1000 mm. The fabrics can also be coated, rubberised and cured to form a composite product.

The paper explores the principle of the fabric forming and the weave structure developed by us in three topics, introduces the weaving process in detail and also discusses some problems which should be noticed in weaving with this new structure.

PUT THE THREAD-LINKED DOUBLE-WALL PREFORM TO TRIAL BY USING FACE-TO-FACE FORMING PRINCIPLE OF WARP PILE FABRICS

Up to now, it seems that there are some common character between the forming principle of warp pile fabrics produced on the face-to-face principle and the thread-linked box-beam preform.

The typical product of warp pile fabrics are velvet-plain and high-pile fabrics. Figure 1 shows the vertical section of velvet-plain before cutting pile. It can be seen that two separate ground fabrics with a space between them, each of which with its own warp and weft, are woven on the unstitched double-cloth principle, while the pile warp threads interlace alternately with the picks of both fabrics and thus link them together. Through cutting pile, two cloths are thus formed -the bottom cloth with the pile facing up, and the top cloth with a similar pile facing down. The distance between the ground fabrics is regulated according to the required length of pile. For example, 2 mm for velvet-plain, 10 mm for high-pile fabrics. One of the keys is how to control regularly the threads length between double-cloth, which can be the length from 10 mm to 1000 mm, and even above while we put the thread-linked box-beam preform to trial by using the forming principle of warp pile fabrics produced on the face-to-face principle. So, we make a weaving on a hand-loom, adopting the follow methods:(1) hand-lengthen threads between cloths;(2) changing the order of pile interlacing. The results have shown that:

The threads length between the face cloth and the back cloth is not regular, there is a wide variation.

The number quantity of pile interlacing places is too small for utility box-beam preform.

Figure 1: The vertical section of velvet-plain

PUT THE THREAD-LINKED DOUBLE-WALL CLOTHS TO TRIAL BY USING VARIED FORMING PRINCIPLE OF CENTRE-WEFT STITCHED DOUBLE CLOTHS

There are five basic structures for double cloths to be stitched or tied together. (a). self-stitched double cloths. (b). centre-stitched double cloths. (c). double cloths stitched by threads interchange. (d). double cloths stitched by cloth interchange. (e). alternate single-layer and

double-layer construction. Centre-stitching can be classified into two, centre-warp-stitching and centre-weft-stitching. The basic principle of centre-weft-stitching is introducing the third system of weft whose whole function is to stitch the two otherwise separate layers of cloth together. The centre-weft lie between the face and the back cloth which is for the purpose of stitching occasionally at a regular interval between the inter-layer cohesion.

The thread-linked double-wall cloths we want to weave is charactered not only integrated by stitching but separated a distance from 10 mm to 1000 mm or even above. So, it is imposible to use the principle of centre-weft-stitching entirely. Thus we modify the principle of centre-weft-stitching. Firstly, the number of stitching places is designed only two for every one centre-weft, one of two stitching the face cloth, the other stitching the back cloth. Secondly, the two stitching places are arranged lang distance apart. Figure 2 shows the cross section. After removing the fabric, levelly moving the face cloth layer toward left until the two stitching places near by, then toward up until the link threads vertical, a hollow thread-linked double cloths appears. The height of the double-wall cloths is the distance between two stitching places, and the linked threads of between the two opposite walls are the centre-weft. It should be noticed that the stitching places of the every centre-weft should be different unless finishing a repeat.

Figure 2 Cross section of double-wall cloths

PUT THE THREAD-LINKED BOX-BEAM PREFORM TO TRIAL BY COMBINING THE FORMING PRINCIPLE OF THE TRADITIONAL WOVEN HOLLOW FABRIC WITH THE FORMING PRINCIPLE MENTIONED ABOVE

As mentioned earlier, thread-linked double-wall cloths can be obtained by using above varied forming principle of the centre-weft stitched double cloths, but this is not our ultimate purpose that is obtaining thread-linked box-beam or thread-linked four connected walls with a rectangle cross section. How to get both sides of the thread-linked double-wall cloths? There are two ways. The one is sewing a single-layer structure cloth on to thread-linked double-wall cloths to form thread-linked box-beam preform. The other is weaving both sides cloth with thread-linked double-wall cloths simultaneously to form a three dimensional integrated thread-linked box-beam preform. It is obviously that, the integrated property and outware appearance quality of the later is better than former because of sewing. So, we try to develop integrated thread-linked box-beam preform by means of combining the forming principle of the traditional woven hollow fabric with the above forming principle of thread-linked double-wall cloths.

The basic forming principle of the hollow fabric is no stitching while double fabric forms and the face weft and the back weft insert cloth fell in proportion of 1:1 strictly. We produce out thread-linked box-beam preform on power loom, as show in figure 3.

Figure 3: The photograph of thread-linked box-beam preform

THE WEAVING TECHNIQUES OF THREAD-LINKED BOX-BEAM PREFORM

The weaving technique of thread-linked box-beam preform are different between hand loom and power loom. We made a lot of experiments about affecting factor such as choosing of yarns, designing of fabric specifications as well as winding, warping, warp sizing, drawing-in and weaving, and obtained reasonabler weaving techniques and technique parameters of thread-linked box-beam preform on a power loom.

Choice of Yarns

What yarns are chosen is depended on the ultimate uses of the thread-linked box-beam preform. If it is used as a general filter fabric, then cotton yarn can be chosen. If it is used as a high temperature filter fabric, then polyester yarn or filament yarn even cavlar can be chosen. If it is used in building, municipal works and so on, then high tenacity polyester yarn or polypropylene fibre yarn can be chosen. The purpose of this paper is to study the priciple and find out the weaving technique of the thread-linked box-beam preform, so we choose $32^S/2$ general mid-fiber-length yarn, the weaving properties of which are better,the preform can be used as a filter fabric.

Design of fabric specifications

Design of cover factor

The degree of cover factor must be appropriate; if too low, the fabric is loose, and link threads are not firm, as a result, its using scope will be limited; if too high, ends breaking often takes place, shed cling, as a result, the weaving is very difficult. According to the experiment, the suitable scope of warp cover factor is 100%-120%, the ratio of wefe to warp is 0.80-0.95. In this way, the fabric is close and weaving is easy. The warp count and weft count of the thread-linked box-beam preform we weave on power loom are 45.8/cm and 37.0/cm respectively.

Design of weaves

(1) The choosing of base weave. On principle, the base weaves may be plain weave, twill weave, satin weave and filling rib weave and so on, but plain weave is the best, since it has the highest number of interlacings compared to other weaves which cause it to be the firmest and the fastest when as the fix link threads. So we choose plain weave as base weave.

(2) The way and the pattern of centre-weft-stitching. The fabric is composed of two system of warp threads, the face warp threads and the back threads, and three series of weft threads, the face weft threads and back weft threads as well as centre-weft. The face warp with the face weft interlace each other and the back warp with the back weft interlace each other to form four walls of thread-linked box-beam preform. The centre-weft with the face warp and the back warp interlace respectively forming stitching threads to combine the centre-weft with the four walls and make the centre-weft an long link threads of the threads-linked box-beam preform. The way of the stitching may be "V" style, in which centre-weft are bound in by one end only at a place, or "W" style, in which centre-weft are bound in by three ends at a place. So, "W" style stitching is termed a 'fast' stitching, "V" as a 'loose' stitching. It is evident that 'W' style stitching is more suitable for thread-linked box-beam preform. In this way, more steady link threads can be obtained.

In weaving, a stitching place is completed and a link thread of thread-linked box-beam preform is formed during inserting a pick. It is therefore necessary that the stitching places distribute in some patterns to make the link threads of thread-linked box-beam preform have the same length and even density. In this paper, a rectangle pattern of stitching places is designed. There are 17 face ends (or back ends) and 16 face picks (or back picks) between near stitching places. As a result, the density of up to 80,000 stitching places per m^2 is obtained. Of course, the density of stitching places can be changed by varying the number of face ends and face picks between near stitching places.

(3) The yarns ratio and the yarn number of complete weave repeat. The ratio is a very important factor to secure quality of the perform. In this paper, both ratios of face to back ends and face to back picks are 1:1, the ratio of base to centre-weft is 16:200.

For the warp number of complete weave repeat, concerning to warp set, loom width and weave continuative on selvedge of hollow fabric and so on, 4401 ends are in the final beam. This value is not only the yarn number of complete weave repeat but also the total number of warp ends. On the basis of the pattern of stitching places distribute, the weft number of complete weave repeat is 432.

Table 1 gives the summary of fabric specifications of threads-linked box-beam preform.

Table 1: Fabric specifications

yarn	base weave	warp count	weft count	width	total ends
32 ^s /2	1/1 plain	45.8/cm	37.0/cm	96cm	4401

The technological process and the choosing of production equipment

The technological process of the thread-linked box-beam preform is given in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Technological process

According to the design principle and specifications of the fabric, the production equipment employed are 1332M winding machine, G122 drum warping, G191 quilling machine, 1515M power loom (fitted with JK202 jacquard attachment).

The main points of weaving process

- 1 In the weaving process, the warp yarns are subjected to rubbing seriously, which lead to ends breakage and shedding indistinctly. To minimize this problem, slashing is chosen. It is the key of weaving fluently that the wearability of warp yarns is increased. In addition, a wax stick can be put at the back of loom to reduce friction, the warp sheet is kept close to its face moving forward, or talcum powder can be used to reduce friction.
- 2 According to the require of construction design, let-off stop motion and take-up stop motion must be mounted. During inserting base picks, the let-off and the take-up are activated on the basis of pick density. However, during inserting centre-weft, the let-off stop motion and the take-up stop motion work, the let-off and the take-up are not activated, and weaving goes on only accompanied with shedding, filling insertion, and beat-up until 200 centre-weft are inserted, and loom motions become regular.
- 3 The weaving of the preform is similar to the weaving of the hollow fabric in some way. The weaving main points of the hollow fabric are very useful, Also it is very important that two shuttles must be used, one for base picks, the other for centre-weft.
- 4 In the weaving process, the fell of cloth floats up and down seriously. Consequently the shed is not clear. This appearance is more serious during inserting centre-weft. This problem must be solved by improving weaving technique. Otherwise, interlace disorders even flying shuttle occurs. The horizontal increasing pressure motion is equiped near shed, to minimize floating range.
- 5 Picking power and pick tension should be controled strictly. If they are higher, centre-weft drags the stitching ends aside,the appearance of fabrics emerges small holes. If picking power is lower, the shuttle can't arrive opposite box. If pick tension is lower, the centre-weft in cloth is looser and longer than other centre-weft.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Through exploring for the structure and technique of the thread-linked box-beam preform, we obtain the design principle and the keys of weaving technology of the fabric. The principle of fabric forming and the weave structure developed by us is new. It will certainly have a great value in developing and producing a new type of textile composites.

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